

Fig. S7A

Fig. S7A. Morphometric PCA plots of fruiting traits ($n = 8$) of *C. quamash*: CAQUbre (blue), CAQUlin (tan-yellow-gold). Plot A axes imply admixture (PC1-2 = 46%) of California *C. q. linearis* and distant Pacific NW *C. q. ssp. breviflora* (CCT, FVC, ZUM). In broad sampling (see D5), removal of wet-east transition zone CCT reveals less overlap between the subspecies. See Fig. 10A, 10B. Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table1, Fig. 2 map.

Fig. S7B Calif. only

Fig. S7B. Morphometric PCA plots of fruiting traits (n =8) of *C. quamash*: CAQubre (blue), CAQUlin (tan-yellow-gold). In B, ordination of only California plants partly divides these disputed subspecies. In broad sampling (see D5), removal of west-east transition zone CCT also reveals less overlap between the subspecies. See Fig. 10A, 10B; Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table1, Fig. 2 map.